

EFFECTIVENESS OF ORGANIZATIONAL LEADERSHIP ALIGNMENT ON WORK EFFECTIVENESS AMONG HYBRID AGILE TRANSFORMATION BASED SOFTWARE EMPLOYEES

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is the determination of the factors of organizational leadership alignment affecting the work effectiveness in the context of the employees of hybrid agile software organizations. The participants of the study are the employees of a hybrid software development organizations in the context of American software organizations. The number of respondents of the study is 100 and the method used to analyze the data of the study is regression. The findings of the study showed that the organizational alignment affected the work effectiveness of the employees in the hybrid agile software organization, to a great extent.

Keywords: Agile Transformation, Work Effectiveness, Hybrid Agile, Software Project Management, Organizational Leadership Alignment

INTRODUCTION

The concept of hybrid agile refers to the blend of the agile techniques with the other techniques that are non-agile in nature. For instance, an effort which requires detailed requirements, accompanied by the sprints of the incremental delivery will be a hybrid approach. SAFE (Scaled Agile Framework) refers to the set of the workflow and organizational patterns for the implementation of the agile practices at an organizational scale. Framework refers to the knowledge system which comprises of structured direction on the duties and responsibilities, ways of planning and managing the work and the values to be upheld.

Reduction of the organizational effectiveness, fastness, development and capability of satisfying increased number of stakeholders are the features of hybrid agile software development. In this context, several organizations are increasing agile techniques all through their organization and trying to identify an appropriate balance amidst the consistency and speed of the outcomes. Our study reveals that through the adoption of main beliefs of successful programs of agile techniques, comprising of customer-oriented and having a sense of shared purpose, organizations of every size may develop rapidly and obtain a hike in the performance in business. But, more care has to be given while scaling of agile is done. Several organizations are utilizing off-the-shelf methods by not customizing them into the problem at hand. Single business units scale agile by not considering the broader business effect, in this way.

For an effective scaling of agile working techniques, a very cautious analysis has to be done from as-is state of the organization in all the culture, structures, operating models and system interdependencies.

Such an analysis has to consider the forthcoming six facts that had been understood from the work done for transforming a big business.

1. Organizational structure

It refers to the way in which hierarchical and silos structures affect the decision-making, the best way in which the team networks are aligned to the goals of the product and objectives of the organization and the way in which the structures help in promoting learning process throughout the organization.

2. Leadership styles and management

It refers to finding out whether the leadership which is driven by purpose is in place, in which all the teams work for the vision of the organization. It also refers to finding out whether the delegated leadership and the teams are working in a transparent and responsible manner towards the accomplishment of results.

3. Development approach

This refers to the identification of the fact whether the business focuses over products or projects. It also helps to identify whether the waterfall methodology is the defining feature regarding development or the products are established in a fast mode in the cross-functional teams, product streams along with assessable effects in market. if the work is based on projects, this factor identified the extent of change which is required for achieving agile in all the working ways. Also, if the business requires both product and project-based working ways, this factor helps to identify the level of customization needed to scale the constructs of agile.

4. Flow analysis

This factor helps to identify the level to which the work items effectively flow upwards (exploration-design) as well as downstream (feature build-deployment).

5. Funding and governance structures

The factor mentioned here explores whether the process of budgeting is aligned with the market and also whether it has been adjusted iteratively on the basis of the learned facts of product development.

6. Continuous learning and culture of innovation

The factor explains the way in which an organization carried out the process of improvement management, knowledge sharing, innovation practices and competence development effectively.

RESEARCH GAP

The study helps in filling the research gap through the provision of a holistic view regarding the transformation practice of a large-scale. Also, the study will be beneficial for the managers in getting an outline regarding the topic as well as the structure for identifying the gaps in their approaches of transformation.

OBJECTIVE

The purpose of the study is to explore the organizational leadership alignment factors which affect the work effectiveness of the employees of a hybrid agile software organization.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Maarit, Laanti (2017) stated that several firms are undergoing agile transformation on a large-scale basis, however, they confront issues regarding assessment while the transformation process has attained the goals or has communicated the results which the organizations are expecting. On the basis of experiences, the authors had framed a model of agile transformation carried out on a large-scale basis. This model had been tested within a pilot organization. The developed model had been well-received and was considered for usage as step-by-step technique for helping the firm in undertaking the next step of their agile transformation.

Kalenda, Martin et al., (2018) reported that the software development through agile techniques have reached heights. It had been adopted by several organizations. But, making a shift of agile techniques in larger projects is a complicated task and has got several challenges to be faced. The aim of the study was to review the success factors, challenges and practices to scale agile, from the perspectives of a big software organization and also from prior studies. The authors had explored the most crucial factors.

They had carried out literature reviews for exploring the significance of the scaling practice, success factors and challenges. The findings from the literature review were used in guiding the action research in a software organization for scaling the processes of agile. The major success factors identified through the study were value unification, management support, lean experience, agile experience and company culture.

The challenges explored were integration in the pre-existing business processes which are non-agile, concern for quality assurance, overly aggressive roll-out time frame and resistance to changes. It was proposed through the study that the organization need not follow a specific manner for implementing agile, but it can tailor the process as per the requirements by holding the main principles and values of the agile methods.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The respondents of the study are the employees of agile based software development organization in America. The number of respondents of the study is 100 and the analysis of data collected from the respondents is analyzed through regression. The researcher has developed a scale for Organizational leadership alignment.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Relationships between Organizational Construct and Work Effectiveness

Organizational Construct is first dimension of Organizational Leadership Alignment

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	Sig.
0.853(a)	0.727	0.700	26.690	0.000(a)

a Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Construct

Coefficients (a)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.792	.243		3.255	.002
Our Working Model consists of a dedicated Area Product Group (APG) operating under the guidance of Triad Leadership	.116	.026	.264	4.488	.000
Our Triad Leadership decides the final priority of Product Roadmap and Technology Backlog	.191	.026	.423	7.277	.000
We have Product Cabinet to provide subject matter expertise to Product Owners on requirements clarification and prioritization	.157	.025	.370	6.301	.000
We follow Simplified JIRA model to have one project under our APG and hold all Business Requirements aka Initiatives under a common Product Backlog	.168	.028	.350	5.985	.000
We have dedicated Area Product Owners (APOs) owning Product Vision and Backlog prioritization	.154	.028	.324	5.413	.000
Our Architecture team work directly with POs to define and create end-to-end technology design of business requirement	.009	.025	.022	.375	.709
Our Design Authority (DA) assists PO and Dev team on level 2 design of our specific application based on the architectural vision	-.008	.022	-.019	-.340	.735
Our DA drives adoption of firm-wide expectation of software development framework and standards	.005	.025	.011	.190	.850
We have an exclusive Data Governance and Metrics/Reporting Lead who is accountable for overall data hygiene and JIRA governance across all squads	-.010	.028	-.020	-.355	.723

a Dependent Variable: Work Effectiveness

Interpretation

Above table presents the Multiple Correlation ($R = 0.853$), the Multiple Correlation squared ($R^2 = 0.727$), the adjusted Multiple Correlation squared ($adj.R^2 = 0.700$), and the Standard Error of the Estimate. The multiple correlations squared represent the amount of variance in the outcome which is accounted for by the predictors; here, 72.7 % of the variance in Work Effectiveness is accounted by Organizational Construct (first dimension of organizational leadership alignment). The summary table, indicates that our model's R^2 is significantly different from zero, $F = 26.690$, $p < 0.000$.

Above table shows that Organizational Construct significantly influences Work Effectiveness. The coefficient is positive which would indicate that all statements of independent variable are related to higher Work Effectiveness. This would seem to indicate that the 7 factors of Organizational Construct are highly predicting Work Effectiveness.

Relationship between Invested Program Management and Work Effectiveness

Program Management is second dimension of Organizational Leadership Alignment

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	Sig.
0.775(a)	0.600	0.592	72.705	0.000(a)

a Predictors: (Constant), Program Management

Coefficients (a)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.104	.236		4.674	.000
Program Manager (PM) helps in planning and execution management of APG-funded road map	-.003	.027	-.008	-.123	.902
PM also manages our APG commitments on cross-business line funded initiatives along with technology debt	.745	.063	.776	11.838	.000

a Dependent Variable: Work effectiveness

Interpretation

Table shows the regression analysis of overall Work effectiveness as the dependant variable related to consumer decision as independent variables. In order to identify which Program Management (Second dimension of organizational leadership alignment) influences mostly towards the Work effectiveness, a multiple regression analysis was performed and the results are shown in the above table.

The coefficient of Regression determination (R^2) is 0.600 which means that 60 percent of the variation on Work effectiveness is determined by the independent variables. To check the significance of R^2 , ANOVA was performed and the result shows a significant outcome ($F =$

72.705; $p < 0.000$) which means that the Program Management (Second dimension of organizational leadership alignment) significantly influences (dependent variable) overall Work effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

The goal of this paper was to collect more evidence about impact factors for scaling agile software development processes inside companies, to better understand practices that work best in a given context. We studied the concrete scaling practices the company utilized, which success factors the company experienced and which challenges the company faced. Thus, we contributed to the existing set of studies about scaling agile with the experience derived from the action research.

The coefficient of Regression determination (R^2) is 0.727 and the result shows a significant outcome ($F = 26.690$, $p < 0.000$). The result of the study shows that there is significant relationship between Organizational Construct and Work effectiveness.

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